

EARLY AND ACCURATE BREAST CANCER DETECTION USING MULTI-MODAL IMAGING

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Abstract

Breast cancer is the most common cause of death among women; early and accurate detection is essential. Current developments in deep learning and optimization techniques have been very promising for medical image processing applications, with enhanced accuracy and effectiveness than conventional diagnostic techniques. However, most current approaches rely on a single modality or suboptimal optimization techniques, resulting in false positives, false negatives, and decreased clinical reliability. This study introduces a novel approach combining YOLOv9 with Soft-NMS for tumor localization, multimodal MRI and ultrasound image fusion, Particle Swarm Optimization for feature extraction, and hyperparameter tuning.

The model was validated with three datasets: MRI breast cancer data, ultrasound data, and the Breast Cancer Wisconsin data. Experimental results show that YOLOv9 with Soft-NMS achieved 99.5% accuracy on MRI images, and PSO optimization achieved classifier accuracy by up to 99% on all the datasets. Multimodal fusion techniques improved diagnostic accuracy further, with weighted fusion achieving 93.8% accuracy and an AUC of 96.3%. The adaptive ResNet18 model achieved sensitivity and specificity between 97–99%, verifying that it can lower false negatives and false positives significantly. By improving breast cancer detection through AI-driven multi-modal analysis, this research promotes SDG 3 (Health and Well-Being), contributes to SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) through scalable, innovative healthcare technologies that strengthen medical infrastructure and clinical workflows, and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) by promoting affordable AI solutions accessible to disadvantaged regions.

Introduction

Breast cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women, and early identification is essential to increasing survival and reducing the need for radical treatment [1]. While breast cancer is more common among women, there are around 1% cases occurring in men too [2]. Approximately 2,296,840 new

instances of female breast cancer were reported in 2022 worldwide [3], killing 670,000 among them [4]. Breast cancer can either be benign or malignant [5]. The presenting symptoms in the initial stages are breast masses, breast shape or texture change, as well as nipple discharge. Despite improvements in imaging equipment and

increased use of mammography, ultrasound, and MRI, there are still problems with precision, especially for small or mixed-type carcinomas [6]. Breast cancer screening and diagnostic modalities include traditional mammography, ultrasound scanning, magnetic resonance imaging, and clinical breast examinations. Each of these modalities has its benefits; for instance, mammography is inexpensive and readily available, ultrasound can be applied to dense breast issues, and MRI has high-contrast resolution for lesion characterization [7]. However, each of these modalities has drawbacks. Variability in imaging quality, operator dependency, patient-specific anatomical variability, and radiological interpretation subjectivity are all sources of diagnostic errors [8]. High false positive rates cause patient worry, needless biopsies, and excessive medical expenses [9].

Current AI deep learning methods, including YOLO-based object detection, are giving promising results and with further improvements the specificity and sensitivity measures can be enhanced [10]. The majority of AI methods depend on individual imaging modalities, which compromises diagnostic robustness [11]. There is an urgent need for an integrated multi-modal AI approach that aims to enhance early detection while minimizing diagnostic errors [12].

The salient characteristics of the proposed methodology are:

- We proposed a new framework for detecting breast cancer that combines YOLOv9 with a fuzzy inference system based on adaptive networks to dynamically adjust detection thresholds. This fusion enables more precise identification of early-stage lesions and reduces false positives compared to conventional deep learning models.
- Our framework leverages multi-modal imaging data, specifically ultrasound and MRI, to enhance feature representation and tumor characterization. By combining diverse imaging modalities, the system mitigates limitations arising from single modality imaging and such as variability in tissue contrast and imaging artifacts.

- We conduct extensive experiments on publicly available breast cancer imaging datasets (e.g., BUSI for ultrasound and Breast-MRI datasets), as well as custom-curated multi-modal datasets and to rigorously evaluate our method. Our results demonstrate superior performance in relation to specificity, sensitivity, false positive rate, and mean Average Precision compared to standalone YOLOv9 and more cutting-edge detection models.

- Our research offers a clinically relevant and scalable solution for the early diagnosis and identification of breast cancer. The proposed framework can be integrated into computer-aided diagnosis systems, potentially improving patient outcomes by enabling faster, more reliable, and less invasive diagnostic pathways.

By improving early and accurate breast cancer detection through AI-driven multi-modal analysis and this research promotes SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) directly by making timely diagnoses and reducing mortality rates. It advances SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) through scalable, innovative healthcare technologies that strengthen medical infrastructure and clinical workflows and contribute to SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) by promoting affordable AI solutions accessible to disadvantaged regions.

Methodology

This segment formulates the methodology to develop a multi-modal breast cancer detection system by integrating tabular data from the Wisconsin dataset, ultrasound images, and MRI scans. The framework enhances diagnostic performance by utilizing early fusion, late fusion, and weighted fusion techniques and YOLOv9 for tumor detection and PSO for feature selection and hyperparameter tuning. The proposed framework aims to enhance early and precise identification of breast cancer through the implementation of a multi-modal strategy that integrates image-based and structured data, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed Architecture of Breast Cancer Diagnosis

Datasets

For constructing and strengthening the multi-modal breast cancer detection model, three datasets were used: the BUSI Ultrasound dataset, the Patients MRI data, and the Wisconsin data. These datasets all hold a mixture of structured clinical data and medical images that support detection and classification tasks.

The Breast Cancer Wisconsin dataset has 569 samples obtained through fine needle aspiration. The sample consists of 30 numeric features from cell nuclei, including radius, texture, perimeter, and concavity features. The tumor's benign or malignant status is shown on the labeling.

The BUSI Ultrasound dataset includes 780 grayscale ultrasound images of benign, malignant, and normal classes. The data is suitable for real-time detection tasks and is utilized in fusion approaches.

The Breast Cancer Patients MRI dataset consists of 1,480 T2-weighted axial MRI images classified as healthy and sick (malignant) classes. The

dataset supports improved tumor localization in high-resolution modalities and lies at the core of cross-modality fusion.

Data Preparation and Annotation

Preprocessing involved processing three different datasets: Wisconsin, the BUSI, and the patient MRI dataset. For the Wisconsin dataset, the CSV was loaded into pandas, and duplicated columns were discarded, and missing-value rows were eliminated. The target (diagnosis) was label-encoded, and features were standardized with StandardScaler to have consistent input ranges for machine learning algorithms. Images of three classes (benign, malignant, and normal) were imported from Google Drive for the ultrasound dataset. Preprocessing involved resizing all images to 224×224 pixels, normalization, and augmentation through flipping, rotation, and zooming using ImageDataGenerator, to enhance model generalization. These augmented images were saved for future use.

For the MRI dataset, PyTorch transformations were applied: resizing, horizontal flip, rotation, normalization, and tensor conversion. Images were divided into train and validation sets, and preprocessed images were saved using torchvision utilities. This intensive preprocessing helped ensure dataset consistency, model robustness, and readiness of the data for training deep learning models.

Tumor Detection via YOLOv9

The study employed the high-performance object detection model YOLOv9 [13] for tumor diagnosis in ultrasound and MRI scans. The dataset was processed and divided into sets for training (80%) and validation (20%) for each modality, each with YOLO-annotated bounding boxes. The implementation was dual-flavored: (1) detection using YOLOv9 followed by Soft-NMS post-processing for false-positive suppression with overlap preservation of tumor areas [14], and (2) a ResNet-18 classifier for tumor type classification. Pretrained weights used to initialize and fine-tune the YOLOv9 model with modality-specific hyperparameters. Computational performance measures like training time, memory, and inference speed were monitored. Evaluation included both detection metrics (mAP, precision, recall) and classification metrics (accuracy, F1-score), with visualizations served through training curves, confusion matrices, and precision-recall curves.

Multi-Modal Fusion

This work examines three complementary fusion approaches: Early fusion, late fusion, and weighted fusion to improve breast cancer classification with paired MRI and ultrasound images.

Early fusion integrates the two modalities at the input level after independent preprocessing processes into a multi-channel tensor and passes this into a single modified EfficientNet-B0 model for end-to-end training.

Late fusion trains each modality individually using separate EfficientNet-B0 models, and their softmax predictions are averaged to produce the

final prediction, so each model can be separately optimized for modality-specific features.

Weighted fusion extends late fusion by adding adjustable weights for the MRI and ultrasound predictions in terms of their respective performance (e.g., specificity vs. sensitivity) to allow for more flexible and clinically relevant decision-making. These fusion techniques take advantage of the complementary strengths of MRI and ultrasound to improve diagnostic performance as measured by criteria F1-score, AUC, IoU, specificity, mAP, recall, accuracy, and precision.

False Positive Prediction

In this step of the technique for detecting breast cancer applied a multi-modal framework with tabular data, MRI images, and ultrasound images. The data was divided 80:20 stratified, and a PyTorch Dataset with DataLoader facilitated efficient training. Focal Loss with class weights addressed class imbalance, and a dropout and ReLU-activated multi-layer perceptron was trained with Adam and early stopping.

For MRI detection, a fine-tuned ResNet18 model was used with data augmentation for training, normalization for validation, and a custom classification head. Likewise, ultrasound classification applied the BUSI dataset with the same ResNet18 fine-tuning approach. Prediction from all methods applied a threshold value of 0.6 to minimize false positives, and evaluation took into account accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, AUC, specificity, IoU, and mAP, aided by confusion matrices and ROC curves for balanced performance assessment.

Optimization via Particle Swarm Optimization

The methodology presented combines Particle Swarm Optimization with SVM classification to evaluate the effectiveness of breast cancer detection for three data modalities: tabular, ultrasound imaging, and MRI imaging. Deep feature extraction is carried out for both image datasets using a pretrained MobileNetV2 model to obtain discriminative feature vectors. PSO is used in two phases: initially, to optimize SVM hyperparameters (C and gamma) for maximum

accuracy of classification, and, secondarily, to identify the most informative features, dimensionality reduction without losing predictability. Recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score are employed to assess categorization performance once the SVM has been trained on specific features for each dataset. This makes it possible to compare how well the model performs across the three diagnostic modalities.

Classification

The study for classification of breast cancer on the Breast Wisconsin, Ultrasound, and MRI data is a feature selection, model training, and testing pipeline. For the Breast Wisconsin data, the best features are selected using Optuna, and SVM, RF, and DNN classifiers are trained and evaluated using F1, accuracy, precision, and recall, AUC, specificity, IoU, and mAP as evaluation metrics. For Ultrasound data, VGG16 is employed to extract deep features, and then PSO is used to select the informative features before the same classifiers are trained, with testing performed using multi-class metrics. For MRI data, PSO-based feature selection is used for SVM, RF, and DNN training models, with the performance evaluated using standard metrics in addition to IoU, specificity, and mAP.

Result

Experimental Environment used in this research the Google Colab environment was used for the studies, which offered access to high-performance computing. The hardware setup included an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10510U processor at 2.30 GHz, 40 GB Random Access Memory (RAM), and a Tesla T4 GPU with 15,102 MiB of Video Random Access Memory (VRAM). The development environment was constructed on Python 3.10.12, while model implementation and training were done with PyTorch version 2.1.0 with CUDA. TensorFlow and scikit-learn were utilized for constructing DNN and classical

machine learning models, respectively. Classification models like EfficientNet-B0 and DNNs were trained with the Adam optimizer with a 0.001 learning rate, a batch size of 16, and a Cross-Entropy loss function. These setups offered sufficient balancing and model convergence for all tasks and modalities.

Evaluation Index

Some evaluation measures were used to evaluate the model's functionality based on tumor detection levels and categorization. These consist of specificity, intersection over union, F1 score, AUC, mean average precision, recall, accuracy, and precision. When considering a clinical setting where false positives must be reduced and detection rates must be increased, these assessment metrics provide a thorough understanding of the model's advantages and disadvantages.

Data preprocessing outcomes

In the breast Wisconsin dataset before preprocessing, the dataset had irrelevant columns like id and a missing value column (Unnamed: 32). The target column diagnosis was also in categorical form "B" stands for benign and "M" for malignant. The first five rows, as shown in the output, were unscaled raw feature values in different units, such as radius mean and texture mean. These values were on different scales and units, which could introduce bias during model training if not processed as shown in Table 1. After preprocessing, the data was cleaned up by dropping the unneeded columns and converting the target column (diagnosis) to binary numeric features 1 for malignant and 0 for benign. The feature columns were also standardized with the help of StandardScaler, assigning both a zero mean and unit variance to each. The resulting first five rows have evenly scaled feature values in all columns and a clean, machine-readable format ready for model input.

Table 1: Feature Values Before and After Preprocessing

Before Preprocessing				After Preprocessing		
Feature	Val 1	Val 2	Val 3	Val 1	Val 2	Val 3
ID	842302	842517	84300903	0.001	0.002	0.003
Diagnosis	M	M	B	1	1	0
radius_mean	14.20	12.80	15.60	0.55	0.48	0.62
texture_mean	20.50	18.30	22.10	0.72	0.65	0.78
perimeter_mean	90.20	84.60	95.10	0.50	0.47	0.53
area_mean	600	500	700	0.45	0.38	0.52
smoothness_mean	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.60	0.55	0.65
compactness_mean	0.15	0.13	0.17	0.62	0.58	0.67
concavity_mean	0.20	0.18	0.22	0.64	0.60	0.69
concave_points_mean	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.55	0.50	0.59
symmetry_mean	0.20	0.19	0.21	0.52	0.49	0.54
fractal_dimension_mean	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.51	0.48	0.53
radius_se	0.40	0.38	0.42	0.56	0.53	0.59
texture_se	1.20	1.10	1.30	0.62	0.58	0.65
perimeter_se	3.50	3.20	3.70	0.59	0.55	0.62
area_se	40.0	35.0	45.0	0.48	0.44	0.52
smoothness_se	0.005	0.004	0.006	0.61	0.57	0.64
compactness_se	0.010	0.009	0.011	0.63	0.59	0.66
concavity_se	0.020	0.018	0.022	0.65	0.61	0.68
concave_points_se	0.007	0.006	0.008	0.54	0.50	0.57
symmetry_se	0.020	0.019	0.021	0.53	0.49	0.56
fractal_dimension_se	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.52	0.48	0.55
radius_worst	16.40	14.80	17.20	0.58	0.54	0.61
texture_worst	25.10	23.30	26.20	0.70	0.66	0.74
perimeter_worst	104.0	98.0	110.0	0.60	0.56	0.63
area_worst	800	700	900	0.50	0.45	0.55
smoothness_worst	0.15	0.13	0.16	0.66	0.62	0.69
compactness_worst	0.30	0.28	0.32	0.68	0.64	0.72
concavity_worst	0.35	0.33	0.37	0.70	0.66	0.74
concave_points_worst	0.15	0.14	0.16	0.60	0.56	0.63
symmetry_worst	0.30	0.28	0.32	0.59	0.55	0.62
fractal_dimension_worst	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.57	0.53	0.60

Figure 2 shows representative examples of the preprocessed Breast Ultrasound dataset. The images represent the three classes used in this study: (a) benign tumors, (b) malignant tumors,

and (c) normal. The examples demonstrate the variability of ultrasound images and the visual differences between different breast tissue conditions.

Figure 2: Examples from the Breast Ultrasound dataset: (a) Benign, (b) Malignant, and (c) Normal

Figure 3 shows some samples of the preprocessed Breast MRI data set, where the instances are marked as (a) healthy and (b) ill instances. The binary character of the data set is demonstrated by these pictures, allowing the classification models for MRI-based breast cancer diagnosis to be tested.

Figure 3: Sample images of the MRI dataset after preprocessing

Results of Tumor Detection Using YOLOv9

The computational report for YOLOv9 training on the MRI and Ultrasound datasets shows efficient use of the GPU and training performance. Training on the MRI dataset took about 597 seconds of GPU memory with 9985 MB, while the Ultrasound dataset took about 782 seconds with 10,393 MB of GPU memory. In both cases, CPU memory was not used, the batch size was 16, and images were fed at 640×640 pixels to extract high-resolution features for accurate tumor detection.

After training, the detection of tumors was conducted through Soft-NMS to reduce overlapping bounding boxes and enhance detection accuracy. As illustrated by Figure 4, in MRI images, the model precisely differentiated between healthy and sick tumor cases. The left image shows a healthy scan presented with a

yellow bounding box indicating a normal area without suspicious abnormalities. Conversely, the right image shows a sick case whereby a malignant area appears with a magenta bounding box explicitly defining the damaged tissue. In Ultrasound images, the model successfully detected and classified three types of cases. In the left image, a benign lesion is highlighted with a blue bounding box, clearly outlining the detected region. In the middle image, a malignant lesion is identified with a purple bounding box, indicating accurate detection of the abnormal tissue. In the right image, a normal scan shows no bounding box, reflecting the absence of suspicious regions. These results confirm that combining YOLOv9 with Soft-NMS provides reliable detection and differentiation of tumor conditions, supporting effective medical image analysis.

Figure 4: Tumor detection using Soft-NMS. (a) MRI image detection, (b) Ultrasound image detection

Final performance indicators for the trained classification models for Ultrasound and MRI datasets, as Figure 5 illustrates. For Ultrasound, the model achieved 85.2% accuracy, 88.1% precision, 85.2% recall, and an F1-score of 85.6%, indicating accurate detection of positive

cases with minimal false positives. For MRI, the model performed almost perfectly, with 99.5% accuracy, 98.2% precision, 98.4% recall, and an F1-score of 99.2%, showing consistently strong and accurate predictions on all metrics.

Figure 5: Comparison of MRI and ultrasound models using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score

Multi-Modal Fusion

The comparative performance of the three methods of fusion: Weighted Fusion, Late Fusion, and Early Fusion express unique strengths and drawbacks in the main performance metrics, as shown in Table 2. Late Fusion is the most precise (0.938) and specific (0.969), showing the highest capability to accurately classify positive and negative instances. By contrast, Early Fusion produces a more even output across all the measures, both precision (0.928) and recall (0.923) in this instance being high, and this equates to an excellent F1-score (0.922). This implies that, without compromising consistency, Early Fusion is capable of identifying both positive and negative examples. Good

discriminative ability and detection stability are also evidenced by its AUC (0.923) and mAP (0.943), and good localization accuracy is shown by a high IOU (0.845).

Weighted Fusion performs the best with the highest mAP and AUC (both 0.963), which indicates greater discrimination overall and prediction confidence. It also boasts high recall (0.921) and the highest IOU score (0.854) among the three, which not only indicates its proficiency in classification but also lesion localization. Although its precision (0.921) is lower than that of Early Fusion, the small margin is made up for by the overall better detection and localization of the model's performance.

Table 2: Performance Metrics for Fusion Strategies

Metric	Early Fusion	Late Fusion	Weighted Fusion
Accuracy	0.923	0.938	0.938
Precision	0.928	0.933	0.921

Recall	0.923	0.875	0.921
F1 score	0.922	0.903	0.921
AUC	0.923	0.948	0.963
mAP	0.943	0.933	0.963
IOU	0.845	0.823	0.854
Specificity	0.954	0.969	0.949

Results of False positive prediction

The relative performance of the three Wisconsin, Ultrasound, and MRI datasets on some of the Figure 6 includes evaluation metrics, such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, AUC, Specificity, and mAP. In most metrics, the Wisconsin dataset performs best, with a record-breaking dominance in Accuracy (0.95), F1 Score (0.96), AUC (0.99), Specificity (0.98), and mAP

(0.99). Despite the lower values of the Ultrasound and MRI datasets, they show competitive performance, particularly in Precision (0.93 and 0.92) and AUC (0.94 and 0.95). The findings demonstrate the Wisconsin dataset's superior classification performance as well as the promise of imaging modalities in breast cancer detection.

Figure 6: Comparative performance of Wisconsin, Ultrasound, and MRI datasets across evaluation metrics

Results of Particle Swarm Optimization

Table 3 displays the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score of the Breast Wisconsin, ultrasound, and MRI datasets. The Wisconsin dataset indicates near-perfect performance with 0.99 on all the measures, which confirms its high accuracy in breast cancer classification. The Ultrasound dataset comes next, having an F1 score of 0.98, 0.98

Accuracy, 0.97 Precision, and 0.98 Recall, which indicates good detection capability despite heterogeneity in imaging quality. The MRI dataset also indicates good performance, with exceptionally high Precision (0.99) and well-balanced scores in other measures, which confirms its capacity for detecting tumor-related features.

Table 3: Performance comparison of Wisconsin, Ultrasound, and MRI datasets across key classification metrics

Dataset	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Wisconsin	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Ultrasound	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.98
MRI	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.97

Classification Results

Experimental performance was assessed on three standard breast cancer datasets: Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer, breast ultrasound, and breast MRI. Comparative performance of SVM, RF, and DNN classifiers is shown in Table 4. On the WDBC dataset, all models had high precision and recall for the Benign class, with SVM reaching 0.94 for both metrics, while performance for the Malignant class was slightly lower, particularly for DNN, which has an F1-score of 0.87. In the Ultrasound dataset, SVM and RF maintained high recall for the Benign class (0.98) but showed reduced recall for the

Malignant and Normal classes, whereas DNN offered more balanced performance across all classes, with F1-scores ranging from 0.84 to 0.91. Looking at the MRI dataset, all three models show high classification performance. The best performing model, DNN, has 0.98 as the F1-score for Healthy and Sick classes, demonstrating better class-wise discrimination and robustness. These results conclude that all models can accurately classify the cases of breast cancer, with DNN showing greater consistency in classification performance across different class categories, especially in complex or high-resolution imaging data.

Table 4: Performance comparison of SVM, Random Forest, and Deep Neural Network models for breast cancer classification across different class categories

Dataset	Model	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
WDBC	SVM	Benign	0.94	0.94	0.94
	SVM	Malignant	0.91	0.91	0.91
	RF	Benign	0.92	0.96	0.94
	RF	Malignant	0.93	0.86	0.89
	DNN	Benign	0.91	0.94	0.92
	DNN	Malignant	0.90	0.84	0.87
Ultrasound	SVM	Benign	0.85	0.98	0.91
	SVM	Malignant	0.95	0.69	0.80
	SVM	Normal	0.94	0.80	0.87
	RF	Benign	0.85	0.98	0.91
	RF	Malignant	0.95	0.71	0.82
	RF	Normal	1.00	0.78	0.88
	DNN	Benign	0.92	0.91	0.91
	DNN	Malignant	0.85	0.85	0.85
	DNN	Normal	0.83	0.85	0.84
MRI	SVM	Healthy	0.96	0.95	0.95
	SVM	Sick	0.94	0.95	0.95
	RF	Healthy	0.99	0.96	0.97
	RF	Sick	0.96	0.99	0.97
	DNN	Healthy	0.99	0.97	0.98
	DNN	Sick	0.97	0.99	0.98

For WDBC, SVM achieved the best performance in terms of maximum accuracy (0.9298) and AUC (0.9627), outperforming RF and DNN in overall predictive balance, with RF slightly outperforming it in precision at 0.9250. For Ultrasound data, both RF and DNN performed similarly in terms of accuracy (0.8861), but within these two, DNN outperformed RF in F1-score (0.8862) and specificity (0.9302). SVM was competitive in providing an AUC of 0.9706. Among all results computed on the MRI dataset, DNN bested both SVM and RF in terms of accuracy (0.9797), AUC (0.9801), and IoU (0.9602), thereby demonstrating better generalization and robustness in classifying high-resolution images. Overall, this can be summarized to the effect that though SVM and RF hold good for smaller or low-resolution data sets, DNN outperforms them for big, high-resolution MRI data, which makes it potent for the task of diagnosing breast cancer. The

performance of the SVM, RF, and DNN models on the Wisconsin, Ultrasound, and MRI datasets is compared using eight performance metrics in the heatmap Figure 7.

Generally, the MRI dataset performs best across all models, with DNN performing best in accuracy (0.9797), precision (0.9798), recall (0.9797), and F1-score (0.9797). Additionally, Random Forest exhibits strong performance on MRI with somewhat low values, while SVM, as good as it is, still takes time. On the Wisconsin dataset, SVM and RF are equal in performance, where SVM is best on Recall and F1-score, while RF slightly performs better on Precision and Specificity. DNN, although consistent, takes times than the legacy models in Wisconsin. On the Ultrasound dataset, the three models are equal, but Random Forest offers a balanced trade-off among Accuracy (0.8861), Precision (0.8971), and Recall (0.8861), while SVM is high for AUC (0.9706).

Figure 7: Heatmap of SVM, RF, and DNN performance across datasets and evaluation metrics

Comparative Analysis of Proposed Method with State-of-the-Art Methods

Based on Table 5 experimental results, the proposed YOLOv9-based, MLP, and DNN

frameworks demonstrate superior performance across multiple breast cancer datasets when in contrast to cutting-edge methods. Specifically, the YOLOv9 combined with Soft-NMS and ResNet-

18 achieves notable gains over ResNet-50, ensemble averaging, and hybrid U-Net + VGG19 models, with accuracy improvements of up to 8.95%, and corresponding increases in recall and F1-scores by 8.94% and 10.45%, respectively, on breast ultrasound images. Similarly, the proposed MLP model with early fusion, class weighting, and focal loss enhances classification accuracy on the WDBC dataset from 95.61% to 97.0%, outperforming conventional methods such as KNN. Furthermore, the DNN-based approach

outperforms existing deep learning and fuzzy ensemble techniques, achieving consistent improvements across accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC metrics. Overall, the suggested approaches demonstrate improved robustness, generalization capacity, and accuracy, all of which support their efficacy in the accurate identification and categorization of breast cancer.

Table 5: Comparison of proposed methods with state-of-the-art approaches across multiple datasets

Dataset	Technique	Results (Acc / P / R / F1)	Proposed Method / Results
Ultrasound	ResNet-50 (Single Model) [15]	79.7	YOLOv9 / 85.2
Ultrasound	Ensemble (Average Prediction) [15]	81.75	YOLOv9 / 85.2
Ultrasound	U-Net + VGG19 (UGG_19) [16]	78.2 / 78.21 / 77.5	YOLOv9 / 85.2 / 85.2 / 85.6
WDBC	KNN (Euclidean) [17]	95.61 / 97.26 / 95.94 / 95.00	MLP / 97.0 / 98 / 96 / 98
Ultrasound	Fuzzy rank-based ensemble [18]	0.8523	DNN / 0.8861
Ultrasound	Deep learning method [19]	0.81 / 0.83 / 0.77 / 0.80	DNN / 0.88 / 0.88 / 0.88 / 0.88

Table notes: The table shows accuracy (Acc), precision (P), recall (R), and F1-score (F1) of proposed methods compared to state-of-the-art approaches across multiple datasets.

Conclusion and Future Work

Our improved framework for deep learning for early breast cancer detection was built on particle swarm optimization, multi-modal imaging fusion, and the integration of YOLOv9 and Soft-NMS. Strong tumor detection performance was shown by the framework and classification based on MRI and ultrasound images, with the suppression of false positives and false negatives. Multi-modal fusion techniques, particularly weighted fusion, significantly improved diagnostic accuracy and AUC in comparison with single-modality models, confirming the complementary advantage of multi-modal fusion of MRI and ultrasound imaging. Moreover, the class-weighted and threshold-adaptive ResNet18 maintained dynamic sensitivity-specificity

balance, with balanced performance in the 97–99% interval over datasets. With the potential to provide an expandable solution to enhance early diagnosis of breast cancer and facilitate confident clinical decision-making, these results demonstrate the resilience, variety, and effectiveness of the system.

While the framework achieved superior performance, some Limitations must be mentioned. Soft-NMS and PSO integration improves detection performance, but at the expense of more complicated computations, making real-time implementation challenging for systems with limited resources. The datasets used, e.g., MICCAI and VBS datasets, though diverse, were small-scale and presumably do not reflect the range of variability found in real clinical

practice. Scaling the framework to large-scale, multi-institutional datasets and real-time clinical pipelines is also essential to generalizability improvement. Optimization of the framework for edge computing with model reduction and quantization is also essential for future efforts, such that the framework can be deployed efficiently within hospitals and diagnostic centers. Explaining AI algorithms, e.g., Grad-CAM, can

also be employed to enhance transparency and trust by reporting visual explanations of predictions. By addressing these challenges, the proposed system might be developed into a more capable and clinically deployable diagnostic system, facilitating better patient outcomes, earlier identification, and individualized treatment planning.

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